

Terpenoids: Part LI. A Synthesis of dl-Trans-Dihydrokhusilene

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4-Formyl-6-methyl- Δ^{1-9} decalene, obtained through Diel's Alder reaction of 4-methyl-1-vinyl cyclohexene-1 and acrolein, has been converted to trans-6-methyl-4 (1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl) decalone-I, which on submission to Wittig's reaction with methylene triphenyl phosphorane followed by deketalisation and resubmission to Wittig's reaction with the same reagent, affords dl-trans-dihydrokhusilene.

In continuation of our synthetic investigations on terpenoids and related compounds employing Diel's Alder reaction as a key step¹, we report in the present communication a synthesis of dl-trans-dihydrokhusilene (I), a compound obtained from naturally occurring sesquiterpene Khusilal (II) isolated by Bhattacharyya and co-workers from the North vetiver oil².

The chart given below illustrates the sequence of the reactions employed :

- O. P. Vig, Gurdip Singh, O. P. Chugh and K. L. Matta, *Ind. J. Chem.* (in press).
- P. S. Kalsi, K. K. Chakravarti and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 2617.

4-Methyl-1-vinyl-cyclohexene-1 (III), on refluxing with acrolein in benzene solution containing a little of hydroquinone, afforded 4-formyl-6-methyl- Δ^{1-9} decalene (IV) in 70% yield which on treatment with sodium ethoxide in ethanol, resulted into the fixation of formyl group in the equatorial position as represented by (IV A). The aldehyde was chromatographed over alumina and characterised through 2 : 4 dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative.

The compound (IV A), on refluxing with ethylene glycol and benzene in the presence of a catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid; yielded 6-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxy-methyl)- Δ^{1-9} decalene (V) in 80% yield. The hydroboration³ of the ketal (V), under usual conditions, produced 6-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxy-methyl) decalol-1 (VI) in quantitative yield. The ketal alcohol (VI) when oxidised with Jones's reagent gave 6-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxy methyl) decalone-1 (VII). It was treated with sodium ethoxide to ensure the conversion of *cis* junction isomer⁴ in this compound, if present, to the *trans* one (VII A), the later being more stable in α -decalone system⁵.

The ketal ketone (VII A) when subjected to Wittig's reaction⁶ with methylene triphenylphosphorane, under the usual conditions, afforded *trans*-1-methylene-6-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxy-methyl) decalin (VIII) in 78% yield which on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid in acetone⁷ gave the aldehyde (IX). The latter was submitted to Wittig reaction again with methylene triphenyl-phosphorane to furnish *trans*-6-methyl-4-vinyl-methylene decalin (I) in which the vinyl group lies in the equatorial position.

The identity of synthetic dihydrokusilene was confirmed through correspondence of I.R. Spectrum².

3. R. A. Bell, R. E. Ireland and L. N. Mander, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2536.
4. I. N. Nazarov and L. D. Bergelson, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1953, **47**, 5368; *J. Ger. Chem. USSR*, 1952, **22**, 449.
5. Bordwell, 'Organic Chemistry', The Macmillan Co., New York, London, 1963, p. 822.
6. R. Greenwald, M. Chaykovsky and E. Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.
7. R. Church and R. Ireland, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 17.

EXPERIMENTAL

M.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. Microanalysis by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. absorption spectra recorded on Perkin Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film.

4-Formyl-6-methyl- Δ^{1-9} decalene (IV A): A mixture of the diene (III) (5.5 g.), acrolein (15.5 g.) and hydroquinone (0.2 g.) in anhydrous benzene (200 ml.) was refluxed for 16 hr., cooled and the solvent distilled off. The product was chromatographed on alumina, eluting with 20% benzene-pet.ether (b.p. 40–60°) mixture. This was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to obtain 4-formyl-6-methyl- Δ^{1-9} decalene (IV) b.p. 133–35°/5 mm.

The compound (IV) was warmed with sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.75 g. of sodium and 25 ml. of absolute ethanol) for 4 hr., cooled in an ice-bath, decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was separated and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was distilled off and the residue vacdistilled to afford (IV A), b.p. 133–37°/6 mm., yield 5.45 g. (69.9%); η_D^{31} 1.5045. (Found: C, 80.60; H, 10.10. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 80.55; H, 10.18%). I.R. Spectrum⁸; 2710, 1715 cm^{-1} (–CHO); 1460, 1380 cm^{-1} (–C–CH₃); 815 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

The 2 : 4 dinitrophenylhydrazone of (IV A) prepared by sulphuric acid method in cold and recrystallised from ethanol gave yellow needles, m.p. 151–52°. (Found: N, 15.55. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 15.60%).

Its semicarbazone, on crystallisation from ethanol, afforded colourless leaflets, m.p. 141°. (Found: N, 17.80. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires N, 17.87%).

6-Methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)- Δ^{1-9} decalene (V): A mixture of the aldehyde (IV A) (5.1 g.), ethylene glycol (6.5 g.), anhydrous benzene (200 ml.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.1 g.) was refluxed for 8 hr. under Dean and Stark water separator until no more water collected in the limb. Thereafter, the contents were cooled, PTS was destroyed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and the mixture was worked up as usual. On fractionation there was obtained 5.0 g. of (V) (79.9%), b.p. 150–55°/5 mm., η_D^{31} 1.5050. (Found: C, 75.50; H, 9.90. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.63; H, 9.97%). I.R. spectrum: 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal); 1458, 1378 cm^{-1} (–C–CH₃).

6-Methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl) decalol-1 (VI): A stirred suspension of sodium borohydride (0.5 g.) in dry THF (40 ml.) at 0°, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, was treated with borontrifluoride etherate (2.2 ml.) in THF (10 ml.) over a 5 min. period. After further 5 min., the ketal (V; 4.5 g.) in THF (10 ml.) was slowly added and the mixture was stirred for 3.5 hr. at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then cooled to 0° and treated cautiously with 10% sodium hydroxide (30 ml.) followed by 30% hydrogen peroxide (30 ml.) and stirred for 1 hr. The product was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed thrice with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and distillation under reduced pressure afforded the ketal carbinol (VI), b.p. 145–50°/4 mm.; yield 3.9 g. (80.29%); η_D^{31} 1.5025,

8. A. D. Cross, "Introduction to Practical I.R. Spectroscopy", Butterworth's Scientific Pub., London (1960).

(Found : C, 69.90; H, 10.15. $C_{14}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 69.96; H, 10.07%). I.R. Spectrum : 3450 cm^{-1} (-OH); 1050 cm^{-1} (Broad band -CH and ketal).

6-Methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl) decalone-1, (VII A) : To the ketal carbinol (VI) (3.5 g.) in acetone (30 ml.) was added Jones's Reagent (3.9 ml.) dropwise at 0°. The mixture was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and extracted thrice with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, 10% sodium bicarbonate solution and then again with water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was refluxed with sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.5 g. of sodium and 20 ml. of absolute ethanol) for 2 hr. and worked up in the usual way to give *trans*-6-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl) decalone-1 (VII A), b.p. 140–42°/6 mm.; yield 3.1 g. (83.1%); η_D^{31} 1.5020. (Found : C, 70.60; H, 9.25. $C_{14}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 70.55; H, 9.31%) I.R. spectrum : 1710 cm^{-1} (-C = O); 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal); 1460, 1380 cm^{-1} (-C-CH₃).

Trans-1-methylene-6-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl) decalin (VIII) : A solution of methyl sulphanyl carbanion [prepared under nitrogen, from sodium hydride (1.2 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (12 ml.)] on treatment with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (10.1 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (25 ml.) gave the required methylene triphenyl phosphorane. After stirring at room temperature for 10 min., the ketal ketone VII (3.0 g.) in THF (12 ml.) was added and stirring continued for 2 hr. at 50° under nitrogen. The reaction mixture was cooled and added into cold water. The organic material was taken up in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and washed thrice with cold water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was percolated through neutral alumina and eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). After evaporation of the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to afford the compound (VIII) (2.45 g.) in 81.6% yield, b.p. 130–31°/5mm.; η_D^{31} 1.5120. (Found : C, 76.30; H, 10.20; $C_{15}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 76.22; H, 10.24%). I.R. spectrum : 3075, 1650, 888 cm^{-1} (-C = CH₂); 1055 cm^{-1} (ketal), 1460, 1380 cm^{-1} (-C-CH₃).

Trans-1-methylene-4-formyl-6-methyl-decalin (IX) : The ketal (VIII) (2.25 g.) was treated with a mixture of acetone (40 ml.) and 10% hydrochloric acid (11.5 ml.) and kept at room temperature for 2 hr. with occasional shaking. It was diluted with sodium chloride solution and the organic material was extracted thoroughly with ether. The extract was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried (Na₂SO₄). After evaporating the solvent the residue was vac-distilled to give the aldehyde (IX) as a colourless oil, b.p. 120.22°/5 mm.; yield 1.65 g. (86.6%). η_D^{31} 1.5070. (Found : C, 81.24; H, 10.40. $C_{13}H_{20}O$ requires C, 81.20; H, 10.48%). I.R. spectrum : 2700, 1720 cm^{-1} (-CHO); 3075, 1650, 888 cm^{-1} (-C = CH₂); 1460, 1380 cm^{-1} (-C-CH₃).

Trans-6-methyl-4-vinyl-1-methylene decalin (I) : A solution of sodium methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (0.70 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (7.0 ml.). This on treatment with methyltriphenyl phosphonium iodide (6.0 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (15 ml.) furnished the ylid. After stirring the ylid for 10 min., the compound (IX; 1.5 g.) in THF (10 ml) was added and stirring continued for 3 hr. at 60°. The reaction mixture was worked up in usual way and the product purified by chromatography through alumina eluting with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°); vacuum distillation yielded 1.2 g. of (I) in 80% yield, b.p. 108–10°/5 mm., η_D^{31} 1.5100, (lit.² η_D^{31} 1.5110).

(Found : C, 88.30; H, 11.70. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{22}$. C, 88.35; H, 11.65%). I.R. spectrum : 3075, 1645, 888 cm^{-1} ($-C = CH_2$); 815 cm^{-1} (triply substituted) and other peaks at 1815, 995, 910, 830 and 790 cm^{-1} . (Lt.² reports I.R. peaks at 3085, 1820, 1642, 998, 910, 892, 833, 815 and 795 cm^{-1}).

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